

Explainable AI in collaborative decision-making

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Synopsis

In deontologically-governed professional settings, human-AI collaborative decision-making must maintain human agency, confidence, and trust. However, AI's opacity and interactivity may influence human cognitive performance and restrain oversight. This study investigates cognitive decision-making processes and neural dynamics driving the willingness to rely on AI for decision-making and the influence of AI's explainability on professionals' sense of agency, confidence, trust, and subsequent willingness to rely on AI for decision-making. We used neuropsychophysiological data triangulated with behavioral and self-report measures in an ecologically-valid, deontologically-governed task. Results suggest that low AI explainability increases human confidence in their judgments and AI reasoning and a greater sense of agency. Conversely, high AI explainability generates greater trust in AI's recommendations and a greater willingness to rely on AI for decision-making.

Background

In professional settings governed by deontological principles, effective human-AI collaborative decision-making processes must preserve human agency, trust, and confidence. However, as AI's inherent opacity and

interactive capabilities may influence human cognitive performance and restrain oversight (Tambe et al., 2019), this study explores the cognitive decision-making processes and neural dynamics underlying the willingness to rely on AI for decision-making and examines how explainable AI influences professionals' sense of agency, confidence, trust, and subsequent willingness to rely on AI for decision-making in deontologically-governed tasks.

Methods

Twenty-three experienced human resources professionals (16 females, $M=36$ years old, $SD=11.18$), a profession wherein deontological principles bound decisions, were tasked with pre-selecting candidates from pairs of resumes based on three recruitment criteria, with and without AI recommendation. Using a scenario-based one-factor Wizard-of-Oz (Riek, 2012) within-subject design, the experiment manipulated the explainability of consistently reliable AI across 30 counterbalanced trials split into three conditions: no explainability (Ne), low explainability (Le), and high explainability (He) (Figure 1). Neuropsychophysiological and behavioral measures were recorded throughout the experiment: brain activity via 32-channel EEG for decision-making processes, electrodermal activity for physiological arousal, pupillometry for visual attention, automatic facial expression analysis for emotional valence, reading, and decision times for task performance, the number of AI recommendations followed as measures of reliance on AI, and self-reports to evaluate the sense of agency, decision confidence, and trust in AI's recommendations.

Results

During pre-decision-making, neurophysiological data suggest greater cognitive information processing and attention in Ne compared to Le and He (Table 1). In Ne, greater inhibitive focal visual attention was applied to identify scenario-relevant information in the resumes, indicated by greater activation in occipital theta and delta (Harmony, 2013, Kawasaki & Yamaguchi, 2012), greater cognitive effort was used to process information, reflected in greater activation in centroparietal theta and parietal delta (Coslett & Schwartz, 2018, Petrides, 2013) and greater experienced analytical realignment was employed to guide judgment-building in the decision-making process, evidenced by

greater activation in temporoparietal delta and theta (Hiraishi et al., 2021). Pupillometric data sustain these observations, showing a significant decrease across conditions in visually evaluating and identifying discrepancies between the information in the resumes and recruitment criteria. We infer that this decrease in cognitive analytical realignment and in the duration of visual attention allocation points to a step toward building trust in AI's recommendations in conditions with explainability.

The findings further suggest more effort in reasoning in Ne compared to He, with Ne showing greater cognitive engagement and attention for integrating relevant information for candidate selection, indicated by higher frontal beta, gamma, and frontocentral delta, theta activation. This greater frontal activity may also be related to the experience of agency (Jeunet et al., 2018). These observed effects may further be inversely related to trust-building with He, wherein they may have plateaued between Le and He. Physiological and behavioral data mirror these observations.

TABLE 1: Significant results of study.

Pre-decision-making		
Brain regions	Frequency bands	Observed significant differences by conditions
Occipital	Theta	Ne > He ($p = 0.004$)
	Delta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.007$), Ne > He ($p = 0.008$)
Centroparietal	Theta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.020$), Ne > He ($p = 0.036$)
Parietal	Delta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.009$), Ne > He ($p = 0.008$)
Temporoparietal	Theta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.020$), Ne > He ($p = 0.036$)
	Delta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.030$), Ne > He ($p = 0.030$)
Frontal	Beta	Ne > He ($p = 0.027$)
	Gamma	Ne > He ($p = 0.010$)
Frontocentral	Theta	Ne > He ($p = 0.040$)
	Delta	Ne > He ($p = 0.044$)
Total fixation duration		Ne > Le ($p = 0.002$), Ne > He ($p < 0.0001$), Le > He ($p = 0.002$)
Reading time		Ne > Le ($p = 0.02$), Ne > He ($p < 0.001$), Le > He ($p = 0.002$)
Decision-making		
Brain regions	Frequency bands	Observed significant differences by conditions
Frontocentral	Gamma	Ne > Le ($p = 0.084$)
	Beta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.040$)
Parietal	Beta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.004$)
Temporoparietal	Beta	Ne > Le ($p = 0.003$), Ne > He ($p = 0.040$)
Centroparietal	Beta	Le > Ne ($p = 0.007$), Le > He ($p = 0.033$)
SCR* amplitudes		Ne > Le ($p < 0.001$), He > Le ($p = 0.001$)
AI recommendations followed		Ne > Le ($p < 0.001$), Ne > He ($p < 0.001$)
Self-reported sense of agency		Ne > Le ($p = 0.001$), Ne > He ($p < 0.001$)
Self-reported confidence		He > Ne ($p < 0.001$), He > Le ($p < 0.00001$), He > Le ($p < 0.001$)
Self-reported trust in AI		He > Le ($p < 0.001$)
*SCR: Skin conductance responses, Ne: No Explainability, Le: Low Explainability, He: High Explainability.		

During decision-making, neurophysiological data suggest greater experienced confidence in one's judgment accuracy and in AI's less detailed explanations supporting its reasoning compared to Ne and He. In Le, greater confidence was experienced in the judgment related to the uncertainty of the decision, evidenced by greater activity in frontocentral gamma and beta and parietal beta (Naaz et al., 2021, Wang et al., 2016). Furthermore, greater cognitive inhibitive effort was applied

to temporize the lack of confidence in one's judgment and assess one's judgment accuracy against what was provided by the AI, evidenced by greater activity in temporoparietal and centroparietal beta (Park et al., 2018, Wilhelm et al., 2021). Overall, this greater experience of confidence may act incrementally to build higher agency and trust in the decision to pre-select a candidate with Le (Karran et al., 2022).

Physiological data reflects these effects, wherein significantly lower skin conductance responses amplitudes and higher emotional valence responses in Le suggest greater positive affect and higher trust in the decision taken (Korosec-Serfaty et al., 2022, Lee & Selart, 2015, Mühl et al., 2020). Behavioral and perceptual data sustain these observations.

Behavioral data indicate significantly more recommendations followed in He, indicating a greater willingness to rely on AI when provided with higher explainability.

Discussion

Taken together, the results show that, in pre-decision-making, any level of AI explainability generates lower feelings of agency and higher trust in AI's reasoning, as evidenced by lesser cognitive effort, sustained cognitive and visual attention, physiological arousal, and higher emotional valence.

Conversely, during decision-making, results illustrate that humans may experience higher confidence in the accuracy of their judgment and in AI's less detailed explanations, evidenced by lesser cognitive effort in inhibiting experienced lack of confidence, lower physiological arousal, higher

emotional valence, which, collectively, may be inferred as higher trust in their judgment.

Overall, this study highlights that while high AI explainability may increase reliance on AI for decision-making and task performance, it relegates the human's role to a passive, non-interactive member of the human-AI team by the oversight of the interaction in building a shared understanding framework. Conversely, low AI explainability, by allowing humans to expend trust in their judgment, gives them an active collaborative role within the team, whereby both humans and AI seemingly cooperate closely as team members to build a shared understanding framework toward decision-making. Low AI explainability thus augments human-AI collaborative efforts when both become more effective from a human factors standpoint in deontologically-governed tasks.

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